

A DIAGRAMMATIC TOOL FOR DESCRIBING HOW A PRODUCT ENGAGES USERS.

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, “how a product engages users” is defined as a situation in which a product provides one or more additional features related to its primary function; therefore, the user has more senses engaged in the product experience. To describe it in a flexible way, how a product engages users literally equals to user engagement.

Because user engagement is a novel domain, it is necessary to develop a new analytic tool for describing and recording it. Based on models and frameworks that visualize design variables, such as functions, user contexts and human machine communication, visualization is an advantageous technique. Therefore, this paper proposes a diagrammatic tool for describing user engagement. Its usefulness is demonstrated through describing how six selected products engage ordinary people as subjects.

Keywords: Engaging products, user engagement, user-product interaction.

INTRODUCTION

In this paper, “how a product engages users” is defined as a situation in which a product provides one or more additional features related to its primary function; therefore, the user has more senses engaged in the product experience. For example, if the appearance of a toaster is completely transparent, a user can observe the bread darkening. The transparent sides stage the toasting process as a visually engaging performance. The other example is a tape dispenser with a simple odometer. In addition to acquiring tape, the person who uses such a dispenser can observe how much tape has been dispensed in terms of distance. These

two cases convey the way in which individual products can engage users’ senses. To describe it in a flexible way in this paper, how a product engages users literally equals to user engagement.

Because user engagement is a novel domain, it is necessary to develop a new analytic tool for describing and recording it. Based on models and frameworks that visualize design variables, such as functions (Stone, Wood & Crawford, 2000), user contexts (Lim & Sato, 2006) and human machine communication (Suchman, 1990), visualization is an advantageous technique. They indicate the usefulness of visualizing human-artifact interaction as well as provide a basic understanding of how to develop an analytic tool for describing user engagement. As a result, a diagrammatic tool for describing user engagement is developed, named as the model of user engagement (MUSE).

USER ENGAGEMENT - A CURIOUS CASE OF USER-PRODUCT INTERACTION

Several studies summarized in Table 1 discuss specific user behavior similar to user engagement. Engagement is a synonym for participation, involvement, and immersion. It refers to a person taking part in an activity in order to affect the activity or to be affected by the activity. In fact, studying user engagement is valuable in understanding how people participate in activities. It is common that memorable experience can be occasioned by a process, prop, souvenir, activity, and/or interactivity. Designers can apply these elements to enhance user participation and their experiences. This research follows this concept and user engagement is defined thusly for this research: When a person uses a product, he or she also participates in another activity enabled by the

Domain	Researchers (Year)	Characteristics
Design	Wright et al. (2005)	Four aspects to describe experience: (1) the compositional aspect, (2) the sensual aspect, (3) the emotional aspect, and (4) the spatio-temporal aspect.
Marketing	Pine and Gilmore (1999)	Three elements to engage consumers: (1) shopping process as a performance, (2) services as a stage, and (3) goods as props.
	Pine and Gilmore (1999) Gupta and Vajic (1999)	Three levels of consumer engagement: (1) theme, (2) central activity, and (3) supporting activity.
Social interaction	Kearsley and Shneiderman (1998)	Three components of engagement in learning: (1) relate, (2) create, and (3) donate.
	Chung (2005)	Four phases of social engagement: (1) initiation, (2) participation, (3) cooperation, and (4) solidarity.
	Falk (2005)	Four elements for live role-playing games: (1) character, (2) costume, (3) props, and (4) stage.
Interaction design	Blackwell et al. (2007) Hoven et al. (2007)	TUIs makes user-product interaction more engaging.
	Nack (2003)	Four aspects of experiences: (1) attributes, (2) presence, (3) temporality, and (4) interactivity.
	Hoven (2004)	Interactive devices function as souvenirs
Product design	Overbeeke et al. (2005)	How to make products engaging: (1) beauty in interaction, (2) rich actions, and (3) irresistibles.

Table 1. Studies related to user engagement

product other than the primary use. The person:

- is entertained by the activity through his or her senses and participation, or
- creates something as a part of the activity and enjoys the result, or
- escapes temporarily from his or her normal daily reality, or
- is attracted by an interesting aspect of the activity.

That is, the person has more senses, actions and/or feelings engaged by the product. As a result, his or her product experience is reinforced.

REPRESENTING HUMAN-ARTIFACT INTERACTION

In this section, three existing analytic tools for representing human-artifact interaction are reviewed. They provide a basic understanding of how to develop analytic tools for describing user engagement. The authors reviews frameworks, models, and matrices for analyzing human-artifact

interaction (Malone, 1975; Coyne, Rosenman, Radford, Balachandran & Gero, 1990; Flood & Carson, 1993; Preece et al., 1994; Moran & Carroll, 1996; Beyer & Holtzblatt, 1998; Wickens, Gordon & Liu, 1998; Cross, 2000; Lugt, 2000; Eppinger, 2001; Jones, Stanton & Harrison, 2001). Three noteworthy studies are presented below.

In engineering design, Stone et al. (2000) develop a functional modeling approach for analyzing product functions. Functional modeling is the process of deconstructing the overall function of a product into smaller, more easily recognizable sub-functions. This helps engineers to heuristically identify the modules of a product in order to redesign its architecture. In practice, the deconstructed sub-functions should be detailed enough so that the modules can be easily determined. For example, Figure 1 shows the functional modeling of a flashlight. The largest box represents the entire flashlight, and the smaller boxes represent its sub-functions. The lines and

arrows indicate user and product operation. This linear flow indicates how users operate the flashlight and how each part of the flashlight functions. By examining the functional flow, probable modules can be determined by grouping sub-functions together. As shown in Figure 1, three modules are identified: power, light, and control. This framework helps engineers develop product architectures and platforms that satisfy a variety of user needs and industrial specifications.

For user-centered design, Lim and Sato (2006) develop a design information framework. This framework helps designers construct scenarios by integrating multiple aspects of complicated use situations into a coherent structure. The multiple aspects include various description models such as function structure, hierarchical task analysis, operation sequence, timeline analysis, spatial layout, and information flow. Essential information pertaining to users, concerned artifacts, and surroundings can be extracted to create the resulting scenario. Table 2 shows a multi-modular scenario for organizing user data. Each column indicates specific entities of use situations, and each row clearly represents a single action performed by the user. Conveniently, each row is also a simplified sentence that is easy to interpret. For example, Action 8 indicates that "the passenger inserts his fare card into the fare machine." This worksheet provides an efficient way to process user data acquired from observation or video clips.

In interaction design, Suchman (1990) offers a framework for analyzing interaction between user and machine that helps to organize and assess problems of human-machine communication. Table 3 presents the basic format of this framework. The left and right columns record user and machine operation, respectively. User operation is separated into actions that are available and unavailable to the machine. Machine operation is separated into actions that are available to the user and design rationale. The overall human-machine interaction is recorded chronologically from top to bottom as much detail as necessary. Some sections in this framework remain blank, because nothing is applicable to the required content. For example, the user does not notice the machine's instruction or that the machine does not respond to the user's request. In such cases, blank

sections may indicate a problem with human-machine communication. Using this framework, it is easier to assess human-machine communication and the rationale for interaction design.

The three analytic tools mentioned above share several attributes. First, they present information in a neat, simplified format. Different kinds of information are separated for clarity. For example, functional modeling converts a complex product assembly into a clear diagram. This visualization not only makes information legible and easy to interpret, but it also provides access for researchers to inspect what is not visible, such as probable modules. Second, these tools directly or indirectly present information in a chronological sequence. The steps of operation are described consecutively. Functional modeling represents more than one user/product operation taking place during the same period of time. This timeline allows researchers to record and consider detailed information that can identify potential problems. These attributes facilitate the development of analytic tools for describing user engagement.

THE MODEL OF USER ENGAGEMENT

This section presents the model of user engagement (MUSE). Figure 2 uses MUSE to describe probable user engagement enabled by a salt shaker called Salt Glass because it looks like a sand glass. The interaction process between user and product is chronologically diagrammed from left to right. Column 0, from top to bottom, lists the types of user engagement, user operation, and product operation. User operation includes a user's action, objects, and locale, thereby providing a straightforward way to describe what a user does with the product. For example, Columns 3 and 4 indicate that "the user shakes salt onto the food" and "he puts down the salt glass," respectively. Arrows without solid heads indicate these typical actions in MUSE. Product operation includes both functional and mechanical operations. The functional operation is what the product performs for its resulting object or function, while the mechanical operation is what the parts of the product do. Arrows with open heads indicate both functional and mechanical operations. For example, Column 4 indicates that "the user puts the salt glass on the table, and then the salt falls."

Flashlight

Figure 1. Functional Modeling of a Flashlight (Stone et al., 2000).

Project-Based Design Information Framework					
ACTION	TIME	USER	ACT	OBJECT	TOOL
6. ...	t6
7. getting on the bus	t7	passenger	walk and stand	in front of bus door	
8. paying fare	t8	passenger	insert	fare card	fare machine
9. searching for a seat	t9	passenger	Search	a seat	
10. ...	t10

Table 2. Multi-Modular Scenario for Organizing User Data (Lim and Sato, 2006)

THE USERS		THE MACHINE	
Not available to the machine	Available to the machine	Available to the user	Design Rationale
7:
8: Notice the card is out		The card is out of card reader Screen: TAKE CARD	Return card to the customer
9: Finish adding value	Take card out	Screen: THANK YOU	Thank the customer
10: Walk away			

Table 3. Framework for Analyzing Human-Machine Communication (Suchman, 1990)

Figure 2. User Engagement Enabled by the Salt Glass.

Because the salt glass is tableware, it does not have a mechanical operation like electrical appliances. Mechanical operation in lighter text at the bottom of Column 0 indicates this fact.

As expected, user engagement can be sensory physical, and/or emotional. Thus, these types of user engagement must be illustrated in MUSE. Arrows with solid heads indicate specific types of user engagement. For example, the Salt Glass engages users to look at the flow of salt. This is relatively engaged participation involving visual contact. In addition, dotted lines indicate that the user interacts with the product without bodily contact. Physical and emotional engagement in lighter text indicates that they are not applicable during the user-product interaction.

To develop a MUSE, it is necessary to understand how an individual uses a product based on subjective walkthrough or observation. Then, user operation, product operation, and user engagement data can be entered. It is important to align related data in the same column, so that their mutual relations are clearly illustrated. In addition, columns corresponding to different phases of user-product

interaction (such as maintenance, use, or after use) are noted in the first row. In this way, when and how user engagement takes place is thoroughly described. MUSE is meant to provide a simple way to describe the user engagement that a specific product enables.

DEMONSTRATION AND APPLICATION

In this section, six qualified product samples were selected and assumed to possess particular properties that foster specific types of user engagement. Twenty-four subjects were recruited as ordinary users to try out the six product samples. The author applied observation, interview and questionnaire through which each user shared his or her actual experience with the selected product after using it for at least one week. Every user's comments are recorded through videotaping and interpreted through protocol analysis on a web-based video editing tool. It took around two months to process the investigation, edit the data and outline user engagement of each product sample in MUSE. To summarize, how the six product samples engage subjects is presented from Figure 3 to 8, respectively. Each MUSE presents several different types of user

Figure 3. MUSE for the Dinnersaurs™, a fork and spoon set for kids.

engagement that is enabled by the same product sample tried out by four users.

For example, when using the fork and spoon set, three subjects among four like to arrange them with food to make interesting scenes. This action makes their table time more enjoyable. When using the weight scale, three subjects among four step on the scale regularly during the week. It means this scale makes it possible to engage users for its functional purpose. After taking away a piece of fruit from the Still Life Fruit Bowl, four subjects among four like to arrange what's left to keep them looking good. This

action absolutely enhances the relationship between user and product. When the toast pops up from the Pop Art Toaster™, four subjects among four like to check the images made on the toast. The toast amuses three subjects and provokes an emotional response. When using the window toaster, one subject among four sees the red-hot wires so he knows the toaster is working. This is similar to how people react to the light inside a microwave oven when its door is opened. After changing the shape of the FlexibleLove™ chair, four subjects among four like to sit on the chair to see how it feels. This chair

Figure 4. MUSE for the Viceversa weight scale appearing like a carton of eggs.

Figure 5. MUSE for the Still Life Fruit Bowl appearing as a still life.

Figure 6. MUSE for the Pop Art Toaster™ that allows user to make images on bread.

enables unique ways of sitting. Obviously, the six selected products do engage users in several different ways.

Satisfactorily, MUSE meets the following five purposes:

- (1) The model can represent how user engagement takes place within user-product interaction.
- (2) Regardless of product category, the model can identify user and product operation, both of which are related to user engagement.

- (3) The model is able to indicate the potential classification of user engagement, such as sensory, physical, emotional engagement.
- (4) The model represent user-product interaction in syntax format, including verbs, objects, and adverbs each of which indicate the action of a user, corresponding product element or feature, and locale of the interaction, respectively.
- (5) The model points out any product operation that is available to the user. It is important because product operation may indicate product

Sunbeam/Oster Toaster

Figure 7. MUSE for the Sunbeam®/Oster® toaster on which there is a small viewing window.

Figure 8. MUSE for the FlexibleLove™ chair that users can change its form .

properties that foster user engagement. Based on the demonstration and application, the usefulness of MUSE is preliminarily examined. MUSE provides a simple way to record user-product interaction. This model notes how a user interacts with a product, how the product responds to the user, and, most importantly, when specific types of user engagement take place during user-product interaction. It helps designers to more easily record, analyze, and interpret how a product enables user engagement. However, MUSE is not developed for other types of design values such as product

semantics, usability or functional performance. Besides, how MUSE fits into the process of product development needs to be further concerned. After all, user engagement is just one aspect of multi-dimensional product features that designers are interested in. The progress of every aspect in product design makes our lives better.

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